

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Implementation of effective communication to realize patient safety in emergency installations

Rizka Kusuma Wardahni*

Department of Health Policy and Administration, Faculty of Public Health, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Communication is one of the factors of patient safety in hospitals. Especially effective communication carried out in the Emergency installations to provide special services to patients in critical conditions. This is important to pay attention to because it has an impact on regulating the number of patients percentages each year. Effective communication with emergency patients requires a specific approach and strategy, which is the focuses on this study. Objective: To identify the appropriate strategies for enhancing effective communication to ensure patient safety in the Emergency Installation. Method: A literature review was conducted using data from two database sources are ScienceDirect and Google Scholar. Results: The results obtained in this research, effective communication in the emergency installations is carried out accurately, completely, clearly, on time, and choosing words that are easy to understand, and pay attention to patients based on age groups and characters as interlocutors so that communication can be effective. Conclusion: Effective communication with patients in the emergency installations is supported by strategies and approaches that include Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation (SBAR) and Friendly, Audible, Collaboration (FEEL) to improve patient safety.

Keywords: Effective Communication; Emergency Installations; Patient Safety; Strategy Communication; SBAR.

1. Introduction

Service to patients needs to pay attention to patient safety factors. One of them is paying attention to the comfort and safety of patients as consumers in hospitals in order to obtain optimal health. According to the book Management Patient Safety in Nursing Chapter II explains that effective communication in health services is the main thing [1]. The same in another research explain that Effective communication is the foundation for safe and quality care [11]. Based on the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia 2022, it explains that services in the Emergency installations (IGD) are a benchmark for the quality of service in hospitals, because they can provide special services to patients in critical conditions for 24 hours [7].

Not only providing patient comfort and safety services, services in the ER must implement effective communication. As stated by Safitri 2022, effective communication in the emergency installations is also important to pay attention to, because this concerns the patient's condition [17]. This is in line with that stated by Milton et al 2023 that communication becomes an important thing in the emergency room, especially to manage the number of patient presentations each year. So, it requires the healthcare professionals to carry out their work effectively in terms of communication and team practice [10]. The emergency installations is a center for patient health care, so the hospital tries to increase patient satisfaction by ensuring that nurses in the emergency installations communicate effectively [5].

However, several patient safety factors in the statement above are different from the service conditions that occur at Awal Bros Bekasi Hospital, to the point where the patient died allegedly due to negligence by the Hospital Medical Team.

* Corresponding author: Rizka Kusuma Wardahni

Information in the field explains that there was miscommunication on the part of Awal Bros Bekasi Hospital regarding the patient's condition. From the hospital denied that the health workers aimed to provide patient immunity, but gave baby Falya an antibiotic injection. After the malpractice occurred, the hospital again did not communicate regarding the patient's condition regarding reactions to drug administration [3]. Not only that, research by Wandira, et al 2022, failure to communicate effectively with patients This also happened in the emergency installations at Pertamina Bintang Amin Hospital, 9 patients expressed dissatisfaction with the service. 3 Patients include said that the communication services provided by nurses were not communicative and not friendly in their actions, 4 patients stated that the nurses' facial expressions were less than smiling when interacting, and 2 other patients stated that the nurses did not provide information about the progress of the disease suffered by the patient [20].

From error case on shows the impact of a lack of effective communication with patients in hospitals and a lack of knowledge about the medical team's obligations to patients. As explained by the Republic of Indonesia Minister of Health Regulation No. 11 of 2017 Article 5 point 4 which explains that the key to patient safety is effective communication [14]. Ineffective communication actually causes inadequate treatment in the emergency room, due to lack of coordination and poorly communicated treatment processes [10]. So it should be noted that, Effective communication skills are the key in health services, especially in emergency rooms. So that's why it's interesting attention Zeithaml, Berrirs, and Parasuraman to develop the "Gap Model" in health services. One of them is the "Communication Gap" which emphasizes the importance of effective communication to reduce the value of errors and improve health services satisfaction patient in the hospital.

Based on the data presented above, in this study the author examines patient safety factors regarding the importance of implementing effective communication with patients in the Emergency installations. This theme has been studied by previous researchers, namely Carl Rogers, who initiated the theory of therapeutic communication. This theory explains that the key aspect in forming a strong therapeutic relationship is influenced by effective communication between medical personnel and patients. The focus of this research is that the author discusses the importance of effective communication to patient with give a number of strategy service, which guided by the attachment to RI Minister of Health No. 11 of 2017 concerning patient safety. To make it easier to answer this research problem, the author formulated the problem of how to increase effective communication strategies with patients so that it can be achieve drealizing patient safety. Therefore, this research was prepared with the aim of finding out the right strategy to improve the ability to communicate effectively to achieve patient safety in the Emergency installations. The importance of this research is so that the medical team can gain insight into providing the best service to patients

2. Material and methods

In this research, the author used the method descriptive literature review. The author's reasons for using the method literature review, due to limited time and costs. Data collection was carried out through two data base sources: ScienceDirect and Google Scholar. Search use keywords that is "effective communication" AND "patient safety " AND "emergency installation". The inclusion criteria in determining articles are literature published within the last 5 year (2019-2023), articles in the form of original articles, open access, full text, and written in Indonesian or English. Selection of articles is based on the research objectives, namely to find out the right strategy to improve the ability to communicate effectively with patients in emergency installations Emergency, so the study used is an article that examines the implementation of effective communication in emergency installations.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results of article searches via online databases, 6 (six) articles meet the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. The study Based on the explanation above, the author details the data collection results in a table, as follows :

Tabel 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Safitri, et al. (17)	Analysis Method Communication SBAR (Situation, Backgrounds, Assessment, Recommendation) in the Emergency Installation	In this study use a method Study quantitative descriptive with tools is questionnaire.	The result of this study show that communication effective in the gemolong for noticed, because concerning with condition patient. That communication effective this can be done with strategy

				Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendations (SBAR).
2.	Milton et al. [10]	Patients Perspectives on Care Using Communication, And Teamwork in The Emergency Installations	In this study use a quality method exploratif, data collected through interview semi-structured with patients in the ER.	The result of this study show that emphasize importance exchange information in relation with caring approach, which consists of 3 things namely, need will concern approach by HCPs towards patients, the need for dialogue between patients and HCPs, and the need for information about constraint Emergency installation environment
3.	Herman et al. [5]	Improvising Patients' Experiences Communicating Nurses Providers in the Emergency Installations	In this study use method descriptive qualitative. Method collection data use interview semistructure.	The result of this study show there is 2 type patients experience, which includes behaviour (courtesy and flavor respect). As well as interactive (describe how method listen with careful, attentive, and explain things an understandable way).
4.	Ramli, Rachmat. [16]	Connection Implementation Communication Therapeutic with Satisfaction Client in Get it an Service Nursing in Installation Bad Emergency Hospital Bhayangkar a Makassar	In this study use a method study quantitative with descriptive correlational, with cross method sectional.	The result of this study show there is connection meaning communication therapeutic and sub the variabel with to satisfaction inner client get service nursing in the emergency installation hospital Bhayangkara Makassar
5.	Blackburn et al. [2]	Information and Communication in The Emergency Installation	In this study use method action research which involve interview qualitative with patients and FGD.	The result of this study show that interaction between patient with health care providers are component important and become experience positive for patients. Apart from that, this research also establishes procedures communicative that is practical, functional and reflects service can increase
6.	Hettinger et al. [6]	Ten Best Practices for Improvising Emergency Medicine Provider- Nurse Communication	In this study use method semi structured focus groups and interview.	The result of this study show there are 10 strategies for increase communication nurse doctor that is: Communicate diagnostic assessment and treatment plan as early as possible, communicate delay, communicate in a way details result testing, give information the easy one understood, communicate patient status, verbal communication no can't replace with electronic, communication asynchronous, strategy communication based on experience team, communication with order physical location of the ER, sera use strategy exploitation experience and roles.

Among the various existing strategies, the strategy that is often used is SBAR. Apart from that, the Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation (SBAR) strategy is recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). SBAR is considered to be able to improve patient safety because, communication has been regularly structured to report the condition of patients to other health workers so as to improve patient safety by reducing errors that occur during the action [19]. This is in line with the results of research at Unit II of PKU Muhammadiyah Hospital Yogyakarta, that effective SBAR communication is communication that involves health workers, patients and families according to their

conditions so that it can influence changes in improving safety patient. The sequence of SBAR communication techniques, according to Mardiana [8] is as follows :

3.1. Situation

First, Situation Which What is meant is a picture of what is happening while it is taking place. In implementing effective communication in the emergency installation on critical situation namely by introducing the names of health workers, their roles and responsibilities towards patients. Then proceed with confirmation of patient information. state the patient's name, age, medical diagnosis, and date of admission to the Emergency Installation.

3.2. Background

Second, Backgrounds what is behind the situation that occurred. In implementing effective communication in the Emergency Installation Backgrounds namely by communicating about the patient's background, such as asking about the patient's complaints, treatment history, previous actions, allergy history, and actions taken during treatment in the ER. Apart from that, you can also add an explanation regarding the examination results which are supported by laboratory results, or explain clinical information that supports the patient's vital signs.

3.3. Assessments

Third, Assessments an examination of a problem. In implementing effective communication in the Emergency Installation Assessment this can be done with an explanation regarding the results of the most recent complete assessment of the Emergency Installation patient, for example mental status, emotional status, skin condition and oxygen saturation while in the Emergency Installation. You can also include additional information regarding possible problems that the patient will face when in the Emergency Installation, such as disorders respiratory, neurological disorders, and others.

3.4. Recommendations

Fourth, is an action where asking for advice on the correct action that should be taken for the problem. In implementing effective communication in the Emergency Installation Recommendations performed with provide information regarding further action according to the patient's condition while in the Emergency Installation, such as whether the client is admitted to the inpatient room or moved to another hospital. After the service at the emergency Installation is completed, it is hoped that the patient will be able to communicate with health personnel regarding self-care instructions, such as taking the appropriate dose of medication, as well as various efforts to speed up recovery or regarding control at a specialist clinic.

3.5. FELL (Friendly, Audible, Collaboration)

In this way the author provides an innovative approach to effective communication with patients known as FELL (Friendly, Audible, Collaboration). FELL is a good communication relationship between nurses and patients in the ER, so that patients can feel emotional support, be understood and treated with attention by health workers. This is in line with Morris [12] who explains that, It's important for doctors and nurses to have the ability to communicate emotionally, and be able to empathize with others. Nurses with emotional intelligence care for patients, develop more therapeutic relationships, and have more compassion for patients and their families. These characteristics are important and can affect the quality of clinical practice as it relates to patient safety. As for FELL explained as follows;

3.5.1. Friendly

First, Friendly. Friendly This means that when communicating with patients, you need to be polite, courteous and respectful of the patient with full patience regarding the patient's complaints. Friendly is the importance of specific communication behaviors used by nurses and providers during interactions, such as proactively recognizing and responding to patients [5].

3.5.2. Audible

Second, namely Audible. Audible related to communication and information delivery from health workers to patients in the emergency installation, ensuring clearly and ease to understanding. This has a positive impact on the patient safety level when health workers effectively convey information.

3.5.3. Collaboration

Third, namely Collaboration. This refers to the relationship between health workers and the patient's family. Enabling the exchange of accurate information about the patient's condition. This collaboration facilitates nurses in making informed decisions for accurate diagnose.

4. Conclusion

The conclusion in this study answer the problem formulation concerning effective communication strategies for emergency installation patients, It emphasizes the importance of paying attention to communication, choosing easily understandable words, and considering the age group and character of the patient as the interlocutor to ensure effective communication. Additionally, effective communication with emergency department patients requires a special approach so that it is easily accepted and understood by patients. As recommended by WHO, Called SBAR method (Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendations) is considered to improve patient safety. Furthermore, the author also developed an innovative effective communication approach for patients, called FELL method (Friendly, Audible, Collaboration). Therefore, implementing this approach will facilitate health workers in effectively communicating with patients, consequently enhancing patient safety.

Compliance with ethical standards

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